

Mandarese Muslims

also known as “Suku Bangsa Mandar”, “Mandarese”

By Vivek Neelakantan, Independent Historian/ Universitas Airlangga

Entry tags: Religious Group, Sufism, Islamic Traditions

The Mandarese, historically a seafaring group and professing Islam since the 17th century (with a population of approximately 1 million), are an Indonesian ethnic group from the province of West Sulawesi (Sulawesi Barat). But their cultural heartland is constituted by the southern part of the island of Sulawesi (the undivided province of Sulawesi Selatan) that was bifurcated into Sulawesi Selatan (South Sulawesi) and Sulawesi Barat (West Sulawesi) in 2004. The Mandarese speak Mandar, a relative of the Toraja- Sa'dan language that belongs to the Northern sub-group of the South Sulawesi group of languages of the Malayo-Polynesian group of the Austronesian language family.

Date Range: 1593 CE - 2004 CE

Region: Mandar River Valley & Polewali

Region tags: Indonesia, West Sulawesi

Map of Mandar river in West Sulawesi, the original homeland of the Mandarese. The smaller square is Polewali, which is the capital of Polewali Mandar Regency in West Sulawesi.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Muhammad Buana, "Borrowing 'Adat' and Bargaining Islam: The Creation and Islamization of Customary Law in Mandar," in *Islamic Law in the Indian Ocean World: Texts, Ideas and Practices*, edited by Mahmood Kooria and Sanne Ravensbergen (Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, 2022), 64-87.
- Source 2: Heather Sutherland, *Seaways and Gatekeepers: Trade and State in Eastern Archipelagos of Southeast Asia, 1600-c. 1906* (Singapore: NUS Press, 2021).
- Source 3: R. Anderson Sutton, *Calling Back the Spirit: Music, Dance and Cultural Politics in Lowland South Sulawesi* (Oxford: Oxford University Press, 2002).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: Zulfa Azizah, "Sejarah Asal Usul dan Peradaban Suku Mandar," 50detik, Posted on December 21, 2018. <https://www.50detik.com/blog/sejarah-asal-usul-dan-peradaban-suku-mandar/>
- Source 1 Description: The word Mandar etymologically refers to three things: (a) the abstract notion of Sipamandar or communal solidarity among the Mandarese; (b) the word Mandar in the narrative of the Balanipa refers to river; (c) a derivative from Arabic expression Nadara-Yanduru-Nadra, denoting a

sparsely populated place.

– Source 2 URL: Idaman Idaman, " Agama Nelayan: Islam Lokal di Tanah Mandar," *Jurnal Ilmiah Sosial dan Humaniora* 2, no. 2 (2012). DOI: <https://doi.org/10.22146/kawistara.3974>.

– Source 2 Description: A comprehensive book review of Arifuddin Ismail's book entitled "Agama Nelayan: Islam Lokal di Tanah Mandar," in bahasa Indonesia. The book is about how Islam synchronizes with Mandarese values. The Mandarese close cultural association with the sea is a major highlight of this monograph.

– Source 3 URL: Ariadi Ansar, "Peran Adat Budaya Mandar Sayyang Pattu'du Terhadap Efektivitas Dakwah: Studi Kasus di Desa Panggalo Kecamatan Ulumanda Kabupaten Majene (Graduate Thesis, Universitas Muhammadiyah Makassar, 2020). URL: https://digilibadmin.unismuh.ac.id/upload/13050-Full_Text.pdf

– Source 3 Description: Sayyang Pattu'du: A Mandarese Ritual

Notes: Sayyang Pattu'du is an intangible component of Mandarese heritage, originating from the Regency of Polewali Mandar in West Sulawesi. The Sayang Pattu'du is a ritual that involves decorated dancing horses that are paraded in the Mandarese villages, accompanied by the tunes of the tambourine and the recitation of the Kalindaqdaq or Mandarese poems. The Sayyang Pattu'du coincides with the Mawlid (birthday) of Prophet Muhammad. On the day of the Sayang Pattu'du, Mandarese children are rewarded for memorizing the Al-Quran.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://resolver.kb.nl/resolve?urn=MMKIT04:000586001:pdf>

– Source 1 Description: L. Kaiser, "Feuilleton: De pokkenliederen (Adjangan Sagala) in Mandar (Celebes), *Geneeskundig Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch Indie* No. 70 (1930), in Dutch

Notes: Ethnographic description of smallpox described according to Mandarese and Buginese folklore in Dutch. Smallpox finds mention in Buginese and Mandarese folklore as a "work of God." Medicines were not provided by the Mandarese against the disease but towards the end of the disease, the patient was anointed with turmeric or air koentjir. Raja Tjatjar or Smallpox, the King of Diseases was also euphemized as a brother and appeased by priest singers who would recite melodies to bring down the fever (a symptom of smallpox).

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Reference: Buana, Muhammad. "Borrowing Adat and Bargaining Islam: The Creation and Islamization of Customary Law in Mandar". In *Islamic Law in the Indian Ocean World: Texts, Ideas and Practices*, edited by Mahmood Kooria and Sanne Ravensbergen. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge, 2021.

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Oral traditions written down in Buginese script on Lontara or palm leaf manuscripts for

the transmission of cultural values to future generations.

↳ Are they oral:

— Yes

Notes: Oral tradition but written in the Buginese script as seen in the Lontara or palm leaf manuscripts. The Lontara records deal with a variety of topics and genres such as the genealogy of kings, history of clans, treaty on village borders, magic spells (Lontara Pabbura), astronomy (Lontara Potika), Philosophy of Life (Pappasika) and poetry (Kalindaqdaq). The Mandarese treat the Lontara as heirloom that is passed from one generation to the next. According to the Mandarese folklore, their ancestress was a stranger who arrived from the sea and subsequently married a man from the highlands. The sea in Mandarese folklore is invested with symbolic significance and is personified as a mother who brings life.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

— No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

— Field doesn't know

Notes: Oral tradition of the Mandarese transcribed in the Buginese script. There is a possibility of loss of original scripture as message is transmitted from one generation of Mandarese to the other. This is a problem related to the credibility of sources in history, a methodological problem.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

— No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

— Yes

Notes: Priest singer would traditionally "transmit" legends such as the one associated with diseases such as smallpox. See for e.g. Dr L. Kaiser, "Feuilleton: De Pokkenleideren (Adjangan Sagala) in Mandar (Celebes)," *Geneeskundig Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch Indie*, Deel LXX (1930).

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

— No

Notes: The Lontara manuscripts written in the Buginese alphabet constitute a part of the Mandarese oral tradition.

— Yes

Notes: The Buginese-Makassarese manuscript *Tahs ilul Fawa id* (authored by a Qadi or Islamic judge in Mandar) reflects a fine blend between the traditional and Islamic conceptions of wellness. Integrates Islamic prayers with Buginese and Mandarese traditional medicines. Chapters 30, 31 and 32 of the manuscript deal with possession of individuals by spirits (jin). *Tahs ilul Fawa id* notes that illness is caused by humoral imbalances as well as possession by jin.

Reference: Arafah, Siti. "HARMONI AGAMA DAN BUDAYA BUGIS DALAM TIGA PRAKTIK PENGOBATAN TRADISIONAL PADA NASKAH TAHŞİLUL FAWĀID". *Jurnal Lektur Keagamaan* 19, no.1 (June 30, 2021): 307-40.

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: The Toraja community in Jakarta has established *Kekeluargaan Masyarakat Toraja (KMT)*, a support group to enable fellow Torajan members to solve existential problems such as finding a job and accommodation. The KMT established *Kerukunan Keluarga Sulawesi Selatan (KKSS)*, a support group in Jakarta that embraced all ethnic groups of South Sulawesi: viz. the Mandarese, the Buginese, the Toraja, and the Makassarese. Except for the Torajan people (over 85% of whom affiliate with Christianity), the Makassarese, Buginese and the Mandarese profess Islam.

Reference: de Jong, Edwin B. P.. *Making a Living Between Crises and Ceremonies in Tana Toraja: The Practice of Everyday Life of a South Sulawesi Highland Community in Indonesia*. Leiden: Brill, 2013. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/10.1163/j.ctt1w8h1dv>.

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Although there is no direct evidence of violent conflict within the sample region, towards the end of Orde Baru (Soeharto's New Order Regime, 1966-98), there was a move towards pembentukan daerah (formation), pemekaran daerah (splitting), penghapusan daerah (abolishing) and penggabungan daerah (merging) of regions. The province of South Sulawesi was deeply affected by political change that beset the rest of Indonesia. By 1999, there were vehement demands for the establishment of a new province of Sulawesi Barat (West Sulawesi), particularly from the regencies of Mamuju, Majene and Polewali-Mamasa. There was political conflict due to the bifurcation of Polewali-Mamasa regency into two in 2002. Violence ensued. The Moslem residents of Aralle and two other districts rejected the split because they would be included in the newly created, predominately Christian regency. For details refer to this news item: DPA, "Violence Continues in Indonesia's West Sulawesi Province," Reliefweb (OCHA), October 19, 2004. URL: <https://reliefweb.int/report/indonesia/violence-continues-indonesias-west-sulawesi-province>.

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: No direct conflict but conflict related to the process of decentralization in Indonesia. During the Soekarno-Era (1950s), the island of Celebes (Sulawesi) was one province. But the existing political and administrative arrangement at the time did not take into account ethnic diversity of the province. In the southern part of the erstwhile province of Sulawesi, Kahar Muzakkar revolted against the Soekarno government and called for the establishment of an Islamic State of Indonesia based on the Sharia. By the early 1960s, the rebellion in South Sulawesi was crushed and two new provinces: North and South Sulawesi were carved. The Soeharto regime was marked by centralization of power. After the downfall of the Orde Baru in 1998, the Habibie administration (1998-99) proposed the bifurcation of South Sulawesi into West Sulawesi and South Sulawesi respectively, given the former President B.J. Habibie's roots in Sulawesi. The old kabupatens (district/ regency) of Madjene, Mamuju and Polmas had always felt cut off from the province of South Sulawesi due to poor communications. Although Habibie's initiative was successful in bifurcating the old South Sulawesi province into the provinces of West and South Sulawesi respectively (~ 2004), in the northeastern part of South Sulawesi, attempts to carve a new province out of an existing kabupaten were unsuccessful due to conflicts between the districts of Luwu and Tanah Toraja over the ethno-religious composition of the province. The two regions had different ethnic and religious identities (Islam and Christianity respectively). For details refer Anne Booth, "Splitting, Splitting and Splitting Again: A Brief History of the Development of Regional Government in Indonesia Since Independence, *Bijdragen tot de Taal-, Land-en Volkenkunde* Vol. 167, no. 1 (2011), pp. 31-59.

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Masjid Agung Mamuju is the tallest religious monument with a height of ~ 75 meters.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 75

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Makam Imam Lapeo in the kabupaten of Mamuju.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Makam Syekh Abdul Rahim in Kabupaten Mandar

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 99.9

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Field doesn't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):
– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):
– Yes
Notes: This is true of smallpox, personified as " King Pox," in Mandarese legends.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):
– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:
– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):
– Yes

↳ Humans:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of iconography:
– Yes

Notes: Tomb architecture in West and South Sulawesi was influenced by Islam since the seventeenth century. The fusion between pre-Islamic Buginese style incorporating boat-shaped tombs alongside Islamic decoration(including calligraphic inscriptions of holy passages from the Al-Quran. For details refer Rosmawati, " Typology and Efflorescence of Early Islamic Tomb and Gravestone Forms in South Sulawesi and Majene, West Sulawesi," *The Archaeology of Sulawesi* 19. URL: <https://press-files.anu.edu.au/downloads/press/n4569/html/ch19.xhtml?referer=&page=23>

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: In the province of South Sulawesi, the shrines of Sufi saints in Maros and Pattene.

- ↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:
 - "Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...
 - No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Obligatory for all
- Notes: The Hajj pilgrimage is mandated by Islam. Ziarah is the visit to shrine of Sufi saints.

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

- ↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:
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- ↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:
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Notes: The Toraja community in Jakarta has established *Keluargaan Masyarakat Toraja (KMT)*, a support group to enable fellow Torajan members to solve existential problems such as finding a job and accommodation. The KMT established *Kerukunan Keluarga Sulawesi Selatan (KKSS)*, a support group in Jakarta that embraced all ethnic groups of South Sulawesi: viz. the Mandarese, the Buginese, the Toraja, and the Makassarese. Except for the Torajan people (over 85% of whom affiliate with Christianity), the Makassarese, Buginese and the Mandarese profess Islam.

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↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

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Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1000000

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 99.9

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

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↳ Are they written:

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Notes: Oral traditions written down in Buginese script on Lontara or palm leaf manuscripts for the transmission of cultural values to future generations.

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of loss of original scripture as message is transmitted from one generation of Mandarese to the other. This is a problem related to the credibility of sources in history, a methodological problem.

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↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

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↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: The Lontara manuscripts written in the Buginese alphabet constitute a part of the Mandarese oral tradition.

– Yes

Notes: The Buginese-Makassarese manuscript *Tahsilul Fawaid* (authored by a Qadi or Islamic judge in Mandar) reflects a fine blend between the traditional and Islamic conceptions of wellness. Integrates Islamic prayers with Buginese and Mandarese traditional medicines. Chapters 30, 31 and 32 of the manuscript deal with possession of individuals by spirits (jin). *Tahsilul Fawaid* notes that illness is caused by humoral imbalances as well as possession by jin.

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Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Masjid Agung Mamuju is the tallest religious monument with a height of ~ 75 meters.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 75

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Makam Imam Lapeo in the kabupaten of Mamuju.

↳ Cemeteries:

– Yes

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Makam Syekh Abdul Rahim in Kabupaten Mandar

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: This is true of smallpox, personified as " King Pox," in Mandarese legends.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

↳ Humans:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Tomb architecture in West and South Sulawesi was influenced by Islam since the seventeenth century. The fusion between pre-Islamic Buginese style incorporating boat-shaped tombs alongside Islamic decoration (including calligraphic inscriptions of holy passages from the Al-Quran. For details refer Rosmawati, " Typology and Efflorescence of Early Islamic Tomb and Gravestone Forms in South Sulawesi and Majene, West Sulawesi," *The Archaeology of Sulawesi* 19. URL: <https://press-files.anu.edu.au/downloads/press/n4569/html/ch19.xhtml?referer=&page=23>

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: In the province of South Sulawesi, the shrines of Sufi saints in Maros and Pattene.

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– Obligatory for all

Notes: The Hajj pilgrimage is mandated by Islam. Ziarah is the visit to shrine of Sufi saints.

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Philosophy of Life (Pappasang).

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

- ↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:
 - No
- ↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: The singer-priests of Mandarese communicated with supernatural forces such as King Pox through mantras or incantations.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: Mandarese folklore personifies smallpox as Rajah Tjatjar or King Pox. Colored glutinous rice, bananas and tobacco would be offered to appease the Rajah Tjatjar. The priest singer would boil area nuts, betel leaves and lime in an earthen pot and the sufferer was expected to inhale the smoke. The patients were covered with mosquito nets to keep the hot winds away. According to Mandarese notion of healing, disease is caused due to the derangement of humors. A person suffering from smallpox would be fed cooling food. Priest singers would sing different melodies to the patient, corresponding with different stages of the disease. The purpose of the melodies was to calm the patient when she/he was in a febrile state. A melody would be sung signifying the beginning of the pox; then a melody indicating that smallpox was a commandment of God. A wooden prahu or boat would be sculpted by Mandarese, symbolizing casting off the disease into the ocean, where it came from. A ceremonial feast or Slametan, involving the slaughter of seventy white roosters, would be organized for landing of the prahu in the sea. After patients recovered from smallpox, the Mandarese priest singer would bathe them in water. The Mandarese priest singer would also place an egg in a plate that would be thrown away, symbolizing the disappearance of the pustules. For details refer to: L. Kaiser, Feuilleton, "De pokkenliederen (Adjangan Sagala) in Mandar (Celebes)," *Geneeskundige Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch Indie* 70 (1930): 808-26. See also Vivek Neelakantan, "Eradicating Smallpox in Indonesia: The Archipelagic Challenge, Indonesia," *Health and History*, 12, no. 1 (2010): 61-87.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

- Field doesn't know
- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
 - Yes [specify]: Smallpox, personified as King Pox was a commandment of God.
- ↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
 - No
- ↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - No
 - ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - No
 - ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: Jannah

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Conventional distinction between Adat and Sharia.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: Between Adat or customary law and Sharia, a religious law forming part of the Islamic tradition.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

Notes: The notion of "pappasang" in Mandarese and Buginese cultures emphasizes moderation and transmission of cultural values from one generation to the next. For details see Idham and Ulfani Rahman, "Moderation in Mandar Pappasang: A Study on Law Enforcement of Pappasang in Mandar, West Sulawesi," *Al-Qalam Jurnal Penelitian Agama dan Sosial Budaya* 27, no. 2 (2021): 370-80.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:
– All individuals within society

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:

– No

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– No

↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: For a Mandarese burial, the conventions of Islamic burials apply. The grave should be perpendicular to Mecca, with the deceased's body positioned so their right side faces the Islamic holy city. As the body is lowered into the grave, the congregation say a prayer.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: Day of Judgment (Yawm ad-Din) according to Al-Quran.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: Day of Judgment (Yawm ad-Din)

- ↳ Restoration of the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new political system:
 - No
- ↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
 - No
- ↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

- ↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:
 - Yes
- ↳ Courage (in battle):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Courage (generic):
 - Yes
- ↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Generosity / charity:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Specified as one of the tenets of Islam.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Specified in the Hadis (sayings of Prophet Muhammad) and in the Al-Quran.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Specified in Islam.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Mentioned in the Mandarese Philosophy of Life or Pappasang.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:
– Yes

↳ Strength (physical):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Power / status / nobility:
– Yes

↳ Humility / modesty:
– Yes
Notes: Mentioned in the Hadis.

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Optimism / hope:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Discernment / intelligence:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Wudu or mandatory Islamic ritual washing before prayers.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Sipa Mandar, or community solidarity

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

– Yes

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:
 - No
- ↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:
 - Yes [specify]: Jannah

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

- ↳ Cremation:
 - No
- ↳ Mummification:
 - No
- ↳ Interment:
 - Yes
 - ↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):
 - No
 - ↳ Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):
 - No
 - ↳ Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):
 - No

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– Yes [specify]: For a Mandarese burial, the conventions of Islamic burials apply. The grave should be perpendicular to Mecca, with the deceased's body positioned so their right side faces the Islamic holy city. As the body is lowered into the grave, the congregation say a prayer.

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

|

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Field doesn't know

Notes: The singer-priests of Mandarese communicated with supernatural forces such as King Pox through mantras or incantations.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Notes: Mandarese folklore personifies smallpox as Rajah Tjatjar or King Pox. Colored glutinous rice, bananas and tobacco would be offered to appease the Rajah Tjatjar. The priest singer would boil area nuts, betel leaves and lime in an earthen pot and the sufferer was expected to inhale the smoke. The patients were covered with mosquito nets to keep the hot winds

away. According to Mandarese notion of healing, disease is caused due to the derangement of humors. A person suffering from smallpox would be fed cooling food. Priest singers would sing different melodies to the patient, corresponding with different stages of the disease. The purpose of the melodies was to calm the patient when she/he was in a febrile state. A melody would be sung signifying the beginning of the pox; then a melody indicating that smallpox was a commandment of God. A wooden prahu or boat would be sculpted by Mandarese, symbolizing casting off the disease into the ocean, where it came from. A ceremonial feast or Slametan, involving the slaughter of seventy white roosters, would be organized for landing of the prahu in the sea. After patients recovered from smallpox, the Mandarese priest singer would bathe them in water. The Mandarese priest singer would also place an egg in a plate that would be thrown away, symbolizing the disappearance of the pustules. For details refer to: L. Kaiser, Feuilleton, "De pokkenliederen (Adjangan Sagala) in Mandar (Celebes)," *Geneeskundige Tijdschrift voor Nederlandsch Indie* 70 (1930): 808-26. See also Vivek Neelakantan, "Eradicating Smallpox in Indonesia: The Archipelagic Challenge, Indonesia," *Health and History*, 12, no. 1 (2010): 61-87.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: Smallpox, personified as King Pox was a commandment of God.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:
– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:
– No

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:
– Field doesn't know

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– Yes

Notes: Day of Judgment (Yawm ad-Din) according to Al-Quran.

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Notes: Day of Judgment (Yawm ad-Din)

↳ Restoration of the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– Field doesn't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Philosophy of Life (Pappasang).

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Conventional distinction between Adat and Sharia.

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Notes: Between Adat or customary law and Sharia, a religious law forming part of the Islamic tradition.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:
– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):
– Field doesn't know

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:
– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of

anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Notes: The notion of "pappasang" in Mandarese and Buginese cultures emphasizes moderation and transmission of cultural values from one generation to the next. For details see Idham and Ulfani Rahman, "Moderation in Mandar Pappasang: A Study on Law Enforcement of Pappasang in Mandar, West Sulawesi," *Al-Qalam Jurnal Penelitian Agama dan Sosial Budaya* 27, no. 2 (2021): 370-80.

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moral norms apply to:

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– Field doesn't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

Notes: Specified as one of the tenets of Islam.

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

Notes: Specified in the Hadis (sayings of Prophet Muhammad) and in the Al-Quran.

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– Yes

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

Notes: Specified in Islam.

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

Notes: Mentioned in the Mandarese Philosophy of Life or Pappasang.

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– Yes

- ↳ Strength (physical):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Power / status / nobility:
 - Yes
- ↳ Humility / modesty:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Mentioned in the Hadis.
- ↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Optimism / hope:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom / understanding:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Discernment / intelligence:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Beauty / attractiveness:
 - No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– Yes

Notes: Wudu or mandatory Islamic ritual washing before prayers.

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes [specify]: Sipa Mandar, or community solidarity

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Full sexual abstinence during the Ramadan fast required.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: During the Holy Month of Ramadan.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions,

then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– Yes

Notes: The Mandarese way of Life or Pappasang requires leadership that implies risk taking.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Field doesn't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Consumption of pork is proscribed in Islam.

↳ Hair:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Dress:
– Yes

↳ Ornaments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:
– Field doesn't know

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:
– No

↳ Circumcision:
– Yes
Notes: Mandated in Islam.

↳ Food taboos:
– Yes
Notes: Consumption of pork is banned in Islam.

↳ Hair:
– No

↳ Dress:
– Field doesn't know
– Yes
Notes: Dress is a marker of social stratification among the Mandarese.

↳ Ornaments:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: The Mandarese have elaborate fishing rituals that are transmitted orally from father to son. Mandarese fishermen follow an elaborate series of precautions, taboos and prohibitions to ensure that flying fish will land in their traps. One conspicuous ritual is to change the rigging on boats. The Mandarese fishermen are very particular to ensure that all knots that link the outrigger bamboo to boats are even to ensure that flying fish get caught. With regards to spiritual beliefs and ritual purity, the Mandarese fishermen believe that the state of their soul influences whether or not flying fish will land in their trap. For instance, they believe that if they harbor lecherous thoughts in their mind towards other women while at sea, flying fish will not come near their boats.

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Field doesn't know

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Full sexual abstinence during the Ramadan fast required.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: During the Holy Month of Ramadan.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily

alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

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Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

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Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

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Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

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Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

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↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

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↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

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– Field doesn't know

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Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

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↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

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– Yes

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Consumption of pork is proscribed in Islam.

↳ Hair:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Dress:

– Yes

↳ Ornaments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other:

– Field doesn't know

– Yes

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– No

↳ Circumcision:

– Yes

Notes: Mandated in Islam.

↳ Food taboos:

– Yes

Notes: Consumption of pork is banned in Islam.

↳ Hair:

– No

↳ Dress:

- Field doesn't know
- Yes

Notes: Dress is a marker of social stratification among the Mandarese.

↳ Ornaments:

- Field doesn't know

↳ Archaic ritual language:

- Field doesn't know

Notes: The Mandarese have elaborate fishing rituals that are transmitted orally from father to son. Mandarese fishermen follow an elaborate series of precautions, taboos and prohibitions to ensure that flying fish will land in their traps. One conspicuous ritual is to change the rigging on boats. The Mandarese fishermen are very particular to ensure that all knots that link the outrigger bamboo to boats are even to ensure that flying fish get caught. With regards to spiritual beliefs and ritual purity, the Mandarese fishermen believe that the state of their soul influences whether or not flying fish will land in their trap. For instance, they believe that if they harbor lecherous thoughts in their mind towards other women while at sea, flying fish will not come near their boats.

↳ Other:

- Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

- Field doesn't know

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

- A chiefdom

Notes: Historically Mandar is the name of a confederation of seven small but feuding polities known as Pitu Babbana Binanga (The Seven Estuaries), and which comprised the Balanipa, Pamboang, Sendana, Banggae, Tappalang, Mamuju and Binuang chiefdoms. These seven polities are located around Salo Mandar, a river from which presumably the name Mandar originated. The head of Balanipa (the father) founded this confederation whereas Sendana was the mother of the confederation, typical of an Austronesian organization. Sendana was among the wealthiest and arguably powerful amongst the Mandarese states. Balanipa represented the Mandarese states in foreign engagement.

Reference: Buana, Muhammad. "Borrowing Adat and Bargaining Islam: The Creation and Islamisation of Customary Law in Mandar". In *Islamic Law in the Indian Ocean World: Texts, Ideas and Practices*, edited by Sanne Ravensbergen, 64–87. Abingdon: Routledge, 2021.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Provided by the district administration as per the decentralized set-up of administration in Indonesia.

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Rigid Social Stratification.

Reference: Syarifuddin, S.. "The Interpretation of Symbols in Traditional Costume of Mandarese". Undergraduate Thesis, Universitas Islam Negeri Alauddin Makassar, 2018. <http://repositori.uin-alauddin.ac.id/16799/1/SYARIFUDDIN.pdf>.

– Yes

Notes: The Mandarese costumes denote a person's social rank. The costumes can be classified into three types: (a) Maraqdia: costumes worn by the royal family; (b) Anggota Adat, or state functionaries; and, (c) Tau Sama, or commoners.

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Fishing is widespread in West Sulawesi.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Used to be confined to the elite caste.

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

– Yes

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through the public distribution system.

↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Indonesian government and the provincial administration of West Sulawesi.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Provided by the district administration.

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the local and provincial administration of West Sulawesi.

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Bahasa Indonesia, the official state language of Indonesia is taught in educational institutions.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The village, kabupaten and provincial administrations.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In Indonesia's decentralized administrative structure, poverty relief is administered through the provincial government of West Sulawesi and local administrations with grant-in-aid from Jakarta.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
 - Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:
 - Yes

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:
 - No

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
 - Field doesn't know

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: Pappasang.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A chiefdom

Notes: Historically Mandar is the name of a confederation of seven small but feuding polities known as Pitu Babbana Binanga (The Seven Estuaries), and which comprised the Balanipa, Pamboang, Sendana, Banggae, Tappalang, Mamuju and Binuang chiefdoms. These seven polities are located around Salo Mandar, a river from which presumably the name Mandar originated. The head of Balanipa (the father) founded this confederation whereas Sendana was the mother of the confederation, typical of an Austronesian organization. Sendana was among the wealthiest and arguably powerful amongst the Mandarese states. Balanipa represented the Mandarese states in foreign engagement.

Reference: Buana, Muhammad. "Borrowing Adat and Bargaining Islam: The Creation and Islamisation of Customary Law in Mandar". In *Islamic Law in the Indian Ocean World: Texts, Ideas and Practices*, edited by Sanne Ravensbergen, 64–87. Abingdon: Routledge, 2021.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In Indonesia's decentralized administrative structure, poverty relief is administered through the provincial government of West Sulawesi and local administrations with grant-in-aid from Jakarta.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: Provided by the district administration as per the decentralized set-up of administration in Indonesia.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: Provided by the district administration.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Rigid Social Stratification.

Reference: Syarifuddin, S.. "The Interpretation of Symbols in Traditional Costume of Mandarese". Undergraduate Thesis, Universitas Islam Negeri Alauddin Makassar, 2018. <http://repositori.uin-alauddin.ac.id/16799/1/SYARIFUDDIN.pdf>.

– Yes

Notes: The Mandarese costumes denote a person's social rank. The costumes can be classified into three types: (a) Maraqdia: costumes worn by the royal family; (b) Anggota Adat, or state functionaries; and, (c) Tau Sama, or commoners.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with the local and provincial administration of West Sulawesi.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The village, kabupaten and provincial administrations.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Field doesn't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: By the Indonesian government and the provincial administration of West Sulawesi.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Field doesn't know

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Field doesn't know

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

- ↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:
 - Field doesn't know

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

- Yes

Notes: Pappasang.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

- No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

- Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

- Yes

- ↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:
 - Field doesn't know

Notes: Used to be confined to the elite caste.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

- Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Bahasa Indonesia, the official state language of Indonesia is taught in educational institutions.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Field doesn't know

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Fishing is widespread in West Sulawesi.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Through the public distribution system.

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

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